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The Philosophical Foundation of Conflicts in Society

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Abstract

There is an obvious difference of philosophy with respect to other disciplines since philosophy takes into consideration how the Society can be saved rather than in looking up to scale a (Societal) edifice in construction. It is often been maintained that philosophy takes its substance for thinking from the roots in fact, every deep Social change which has taken place have emerged from philosophical activity. Hence it has been said that philosophers influences the most the destinies of history.

Keywords Society, Identity, Conflict.

Introduction

Society is not merely a group of people; it is a complex system existing amongst the group of people. The truth is that many of the social interactions are always not peaceful and cooperative whereas tension, struggle, selfishness could also exist in these interactions. When such a situation arises amongst two or more people, there arises conflict. An internal tension between two or more social groups is called as a conflict. In conflict the two groups would not be able to accomplish common goals with coexistence. Conflict is a psychological situation in which a man experiences a complex confusion or tension due to which man is not able to interact with that situation consistently. When this situation is found between two groups then it's called social tension. In reality this condition arises due to the continuous revolutionary ideas, selfish interests, moral values, religious values, communal relationships and differences among each other. Thus, there are various kinds of conflicts are caused due to various reasons such as economic, political, psychological, geographical and the like.

Objective of study

The significance of this article is particularly centered on the suggestion that one can view conflict as the product of a communication process and culture as a system of symbols and meanings which allow conflict to be seen as embedded in the normative system of culture. Such a perspective implies that conflict is fundamental representation of identity. It also implies the underlying idea that one is not possible to construct a social system which evades this reality. Hence, the most significant question is as to which way does conflict form a viable basis for harmony?

Review of Literature

Hence globalization cannot be avoided therefore our main purpose is how to participate in it, and how to make it fruitful for our lives.? Socrates, Plato and Aristotle saw how globalization came into existence. It was followed by St. Augustine and St. Aquinas. It was further developed by Hobbes, Locke and Rousseau. Since our intention is to look for the solutions Two principles are preferred; the principle of participation (pointed by

Aquinas and principle of communion developed by Gadamer in his book Truth and method.

Main Text Participation means an active engagement in the construction of society by preserving, and furthering life. Since man's nature is social, and social nature is thus identified by one's own act of participating in society. As such each individual is a part of society, and the more individuals engage in this task, society is bigger, richer and more efficient. Therefore social beings must be recognized as being moral beings. That is why according to Confucius true human being must be primarily a moral being. Kant points out that only participation for the sake of duty to humanity is a true participation. Gadamer's views of fusion of horizon stated in his book "Truth and Method" Gadamer described the horizon as; "the range of "vision that includes everything that can be seen from particular vantage point. Secondly, the horizon is not static, and not even real since the horizon moves, recedes and advances with us therefore it is not the same horizon. Thirdly, the expansion of the horizon implicitly implies a fusion of new dimensions: situations Similarly On the basis of these two principles participation and communion here we would argue that a pluralistic culture can be possible, if we accept that all belong to the same family, that we all share a common hope for a better world and that we all have the same characteristics that are essentially human characteristics. Here Gadamer's views on fusion of horizon can indicate towards the possibility of pluralistic culture.

Concept of Conflict

Conflict is a psychological situation in which a man experiences a complex confusion or tension due to which that man is not able to interact with the situation consistently. When this situation is found between two groups then it's called social tension. There are different type of conflicts like Psychological conflict, Generation Gap Conflict, Identity Conflict and Religious conflicts.

Psychological Conflict

Disagreement, clash, and opposition of ideas that occurs in the mind of individual's refers to a Psychological Conflict There are instances where some individuals have a fear of the unknown (future) because he cannot visualize, what the future holds for him?

Some instincts and emotions determine man's Ego, this can be developed in many ways like social background, environment and others. Super Ego is to check the instinct of man and now the psychological application penetrates into the most part of man through the "Id" and the countering by the "Ego". There is also the fear of death, failure, criticism and isolation. All these are examples of individual conflicts.

Generation Gap Difference

However it is generally accepted that there is an obvious difference between the two views of the old generation and the new generation in any society. There are some things which the old generations believe to be sacred, and therefore they want to accept the belief and rules that are prevalent in the tradition of that culture. There is a possibility that to new generation such belief are non sacred and uncalled for. The young ones feel "caged" and want to be "free". The difficulty to do what they feel like doing put them to disagree with the old generation. The impact of education also causes generation gap conflicts.

In reality this situation arises due to the continuous revolutionary ideas, selfish interests, moral values, religious values, communal relationships, differences with each other. It means when social, economical, political, religious, morals of two groups collide, that situation is called conflict. For example: religious conflict between two religions, communal conflicts between two or more communities or tribes, similarly the conflict between two political groups may arise due to difference of their political goals and objectives.

Whenever we talk of Culture, we always perceive that there would be a conflict since the groups formed in the society wants to maintain their identity. There is a possibility that religion may be thought of to one of the causes of conflict. There can be differences while giving the interpretation of principles and meanings. Therefore it can be perceived that, Religion also deals with the important existential issues of human life, within all religions. however, there is not homogeneity; there are differences of interpretation of principles and meanings. Hence it is understood that,

Now the question arises? Has the modern man lost his contact with the dimensions of reality that gives rise to religion? If religion is considered to give a explanation to man's ultimate questions, then the modern man seemingly does not bother about such questions. The theological concepts and religious values of the bygone days are entirely out of tune with our present day outlooks, convictions and sense of values. Perhaps a sober, theistic humanism in modern times can provide some degree of corrective equally to asedate religious transcendentalism. The crisis of faith that has befallen the modern man has got to be recovered.

The present moment seeks an attention of the humanity, how to free itself not only from the horrifying possibility of a nuclear war but also the distancing of oneself from his intimate self. The only rational approach is to acquire greater understanding of ourselves and a greater trust between humans. Although man has acquired tremendous control over nature yet he has not conquered himself: Unless it is done it would become quite impossible to bring any improvement to the preservation of humanity and to the promotion of peace and happiness among people. A genuine humanistic culture has to be promoted and accepted by all nations. It means religion; caste and colour should not be allowed to come in the way of man in courting friendship with man. It is sad to note that religions have had disagreements with one another throughout history due to different religious codes and beliefs. Such unwarranted fights are brought about when the adherents of each religion are convinced that their way to salvation is superior since there is a difference between one religion and the other. religions. Each religion, say Hinduism or Christianity or Islam, is historically rooted in the cultural history of the people concerned. Therefore, each religion has a historic-cultural diversity of its own. Besides, within each religious tradition, a particular set of religious idea. beliefs and doctrines takes into consideration the need of the community concerned. An elaborate belief system informs the broad function of the religious customs, practices and the form of life of the people. Thus religions exist just as cultures and societies do. They are all tangible formations. Within each monolithic formation, sects and sub-sects arise, and thus there are an ever-increasing number of sub-religious seets that come into existence. Thus religious plurality is a self-evident historical fact, implying thereby that we should make sufficient reasons for an ultimate Being or Truth governing the destinies of man and theuniverse and the actions of human race adopting various ways of contemplation, meditation, payer and worship in his efforts to approach the Absolute. One cannot reasonably argue that one's religion alone is the correct one and that one's mode of ritust, prayer and worship is final, Religious harmony can be attained by accepting the simple rule that everyone has a right to his religious beliefs and also to follow his own religious practices, which he hes inherited from the tradition that he is born in. Therefore, what is to be accepted is that each individual has a unique status of man as human and the worth of life itself. Man is essentially a self-transcending being who has surpassed the given to his capacity of reflection and self-reflection. The physical world has a new meaning for him as comprehended by his reason and superior intellect, and the extent of this comprehension determines the event of his freedom. This continual interplay in man of the physical, mental and spiritual is both a blessing and a peril to him. No creature, an the modern existentialists says, is capable of such depths of loneliness, crime, bewilderment, and despair man is. Yet by the organic development of his diverse capacities, gives a meaning and purpose to his life. Such a life when enkindled by an awareness of his deep abiding commitment to the world, can reach him to the highest strata of devotional life, which at the same time is the highest level of existential realization. Such a realization is the supreme concern of Universal Religion. As As Herschel put it "Human is he, who is concerned with other selves.... A stone is self-sufficient, man is surpassing...Man cannot even be in accord with his own self unless he serves something beyond himself The presence of the deep transitive concern opens up for man a new ontological dimensions: the dimension of the holy. Surpassing the vegetative and the animal, man exhibits his deep transitive concern with God and it is in this that the Imago Dei rests". Therefore, what is needed for the establishment of the social harmony and the functioning of a universal dynamic humanism is the overcoming of the beastliness in man, through his education being carried beyond the intellectual to the spiritual dimensions of his being. This is what Vivekananda calls a true religion, which he defines 'as the manifestation of the divinity already in man'.

Conclusion

There is no possibility of doubting that spatial density and the increasing tempo of living have not only brought humanity closer, but have also caused more problems. These problems are not geographically specific they have become universal. They are our problems, so we are forced to find solutions, as such, The hope of finding a universal solution is givenup because there are no particular values or a single system neither any culture which can find answers to such problems. The principle of participation and the principle of communion are the two busie principles of a Pluralistic culture Pluralistic culture forms an essential part of our life world and it reflects a new way of living guided by rational principles. It is constituted by human beings in a world of new emerging structure, According to the Pluralistic Culture it is accepted that, in a globalized world, no one is isolated, no one is untouched by one's surroundings and no one can claim to be fully independent and free. Rousseau had declared in his famous book. The Social Contract that all of us are chained'i.e. socially dependent and related. But on the other

hand, pluralistic culture which Kant fought i.e for him, human beings are in a permanent process of emancipating themselves from the chains imposed on them, or of getting rid of idols and ideologies (Marx). Pluralistic culture, guided by reason, leads human beings to a state of freedom -to-i.e. a state in which human choice is autonomous. If we can transform the globalized world it into a part of our life that benefits us then we cannot be enslaved. Thus, to live globally means to have many shared needs (wanted or unwanted)², to participate in the process of producing commodities and satisfying them and to share duties and responsibilities to preserve and develop our life-world. Understood in this sense, the globalization process means a process of living which requires that all those living in the global world must have common or shared need and interests, and ii, participate in the process of satisfying needs and interests. Hence globalization cannot be avoided therefore our main purpose is how to participate in it, and how to make it fruitful for our lives.? Socrates, Plato and Aristotle saw how globalization came into existence. It was followed by St. Augustine and St.Aquinas. It was further developed by Hobbes, Locke and Rousseau. Since our intention is to look for the solutions Two principles are preferred; the principle of participation (pointed by Aquinas and principle of communion developed by Gadamer in his book Truth and method. Participation means an active engagement in the construction of society by preserving, and furthering life. Since man's nature is social, and social nature is thus identified by one's own act of participating in society. As such each individual is a part of society, and the more individuals engage in this task, society is bigger, richer and more efficient. Therefore social beings must be recognized as being moral beings. That is why according to Confucius true human being must be primarily a moral being. Kant points out that only participation for the sake of duty to humanity is a true participation.Gadamer's views of fusion of horizon stated in his book "Truth and Method Gadamer described the horizon as; "the range of 'vision that includes everything that can be seen from particular vantage point. Secondly, the horizon is not static, and not even real since the horizon moves, recedes and advances with us therefore it is not the same horizon. Thirdly, the expansion of the horizon implicitly implies a fusion of new dimensions; situations Similarly On the basis of these two principles participation and communion here we would argue that a pluralistic culture can be possible, if we accept that all belong to the same family, that we all share a common hope for a better world and that we all have the same characteristics that are essentially human characteristics. Here Gadamer's views on fusion of horizon can indicate towards the possibility of pluralistic culture. Gadamer compared to our own opinions, that they are also not static, we keep on changing Our views encompass our old views, just as the new horizon encompasses the old one. Our historical consciousness is also a kind of fusion of horizons. Our historical consciousness is not a simple consciousness of something, someone, or some period. It is a single horizon that embraces everything in the past, i.e. our traditions. Thus we can say that not only our historical consciousness, nor our language but our practical daily life follows the same way of life follow the same path by transforming new views new, new knowledge and making them to be our life world. Therefore the world is not closed or monolithic, but pluralistic, and such a life is rich and encompassing. But what I personally feel is that the challenge is intellectual and it has to be tackled initially on the intellectual plane. "Since wars begin in the mind of man, it is in the minds of men that social harmony must be constructed."

References

1. A.L., *Kroeber and Kluckhohn, Culture: A Critical Review of Concepts and Definitions, (Cambridge Mass., 1952), p.223.*
2. Clifford, G., *The Interpretation of cultures (London: Hutchinson, 1973), p.5.*
3. Johnson Puthenpurackal, (Ed), *The post-modern...A siege of the citadel of reason (Delhi, Media house, 2002.*
4. Sorokin,P. *The crisis of Our age: social Cultural Outlook.(New York:Dutton, 1957), p.25-26. Africa, Vol.VIII, (1985), P.58.*
5. Walsh, J. *Intercultural Education in the Communication of Man. Honolulu: The University of Hawaii Press, 1973.*